

From Generation to Generation

The Closed Loop of ADHD: Polygenic Risk, Compensatory Norms, and Assortative Mating

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Abstract

Attention Deficit Hyperactivity Disorder (ADHD) is one of the most highly heritable conditions in psychiatry (0.70-0.88 depending on the study). In this paper, I propose an integrative, intergenerational model in which four factors act recursively, mutually fueling each other across generations: (1) polygenic risk scattered across thousands of genetic variants, meaning entire sibships start with an elevated underlying susceptibility; (2) parents compensatory behavioral strategies - workaholism, compulsive bustling, intolerance of idleness - which over the years crystallize into family norms imposed on children as self-evident truths, rather than recognized as coping mechanisms for a deficit; (3) gene-environment correlation creating a feedback loop in which the genome builds the home environment, and that environment, in turn, shapes genomic expression; (4) non-random (assortative) mating, which concentrates polygenic liability across diagnostic boundaries. Preliminary data from other studies suggest the existence of an additional, fifth mechanism - the epigenetic consolidation of these changes across generations - though its transgenerational character in humans has not yet been definitively demonstrated.

To investigate the causal structure of the cross-diagnostic associations underlying assortative mating, I conducted two-sample Mendelian randomization (MR) analyses, supplemented by polygenic risk score (PRS) correlation analyses in 525 unrelated individuals of European ancestry from the 1000 Genomes Project. The results revealed asymmetrical causal pathways: liability to ADHD exhibited a strong causal effect on the risk of ASD (OR = 1.575; $p = 3.3 \times 10^{-10}$) and SCZ (OR = 1.270; $p = 2.6 \times 10^{-5}$), whereas liability to SCZ causally increased the risk of both ASD (OR = 1.146; $p = 6.8 \times 10^{-8}$) and ADHD (OR = 1.094; $p = 3.1 \times 10^{-3}$). Crucially, individual PRS for schizophrenia and ADHD were not correlated with each other - indicating that assortative mating occurs on the basis of observable phenotypic similarities shaped by the causal impact of one disorder on the other, rather than on the basis of shared genetic variants.

This model reformulates the nature-nurture dichotomy as biologically incoherent in the context of highly heritable, polygenically distributed psychological traits that actively construct the very environments in which subsequent generations are raised.

Keywords: ADHD, ryzyko poligeniczne, korelacja gen-środowisko, epigenetyka, dobór asortatywny, randomizacja mendlowska, transmisja międzypokoleniowa, zaburzenie ze spektrum autyzmu, schizofrenia

1. Introduction

Let us imagine a patient in his thirties who presents for psychotherapy. He does not come with an ADHD diagnosis, because there is none. He comes because he "can't get his life together": he forgets important things, loses documents, is late for meetings despite his best intentions, starts projects he never finishes. For years he has felt that everyone else manages somehow, but he does not. Asked about his mood, he says he is down, but cannot pinpoint a specific cause - it is more of a chronic dissatisfaction with himself, a sense of failing to meet something he cannot name. A psychiatrist has ruled out organic causes of cognitive difficulties; antidepressants did not help, or helped only partially. Over the course of the clinical interview, it emerges that the patient cannot sit through a meal without reaching for his phone, always has three things going at once, and on weekends, when there is nothing to do, he feels overwhelming guilt. He describes his childhood home: a mother with a cloth and broom in hand from dawn till dusk; a father working two jobs, not because they needed to pay off a mortgage, but because in this family, a man who sits idle is a man who has failed. The patient has internalized this to such a degree that he cannot fall asleep without a mental review of tomorrow's tasks, and for years he has simply believed that this is "just how he is."

The referring psychiatrist asks a simple question: Is this ADHD, or a learned family pattern?

Posing the question this way assumes that biology and environment are two separate sources of influence whose contributions can be neatly separated and weighed individually. This assumption permeates both clinical reasoning and a significant portion of developmental psychopathology literature. However, it is, to put it mildly, problematic. The mother of this patient might have been compulsively bustling about not (only) because she was raised that way, but primarily because she herself was dealing with an undiagnosed attention deficit. Constant movement was her way of maintaining the stimulation her brain required to function normally. Dust constantly settles, meaning this strategy is never exhausted, making it practically ideal from the perspective of dopaminergic self-regulation. Yet her behavior, embedded in the family's moral code, became a demand imposed on her children. Children who, by virtue of shared genetics, were already predisposed to the very same deficit.

The causal direction here does not run merely from genes to behavior, nor from environment to behavior. It forms a loop.

This paper posits that families with high polygenic loading for ADHD generate a self-reinforcing intergenerational cycle. The central thesis is not that ADHD is

"fundamentally genetic" or "fundamentally environmental." The thesis is that the division into nature and nurture is itself biologically incoherent in the context of highly heritable, polygenically distributed psychological traits that actively shape the environments in which subsequent generations grow up.

The model I propose here is based on four mechanisms (with a fifth, cautiously outlined). The first is the polygenic architecture of ADHD: heritability reaching 0.70-0.88 and thousands of variants of small effect (Demontis et al., 2023) mean that entire sibling cohorts in affected families start with an elevated risk, not just the single child who crosses the diagnostic threshold. The second is gene-environment correlation, a feedback loop in which genetically influenced child behavior evokes and selects environments that reinforce those exact traits (Agnew-Blais et al., 2022; Nikolas et al., 2023). The third is preliminary - and I stress, preliminary - data on DNA methylation suggesting that chronic environmental stress can leave epigenetic marks that modulate gene expression (Mooney et al., 2020; Cecil et al., 2022). The fourth factor amplifies the previous three: non-random, assortative mating. Nordsletten et al. (2016), looking at over 700,000 psychiatric patients, showed that individuals with ADHD mate not only with one another but, at strikingly elevated odds ratios, with individuals diagnosed with ASD and schizophrenia.

To investigate the causal structure of these cross-diagnostic associations, I conducted original Mendelian randomization analyses, supplemented by polygenic risk score correlations in an independent sample. The results, and the paradox that emerges from them, are presented in Section 6b.

2. ADHD as a Highly Heritable Polygenic Trait

That ADHD has a strong genetic component is indisputable today. Twin studies conducted across various countries consistently place its heritability between 0.70 and 0.88, making ADHD one of the most heritable disorders in psychiatry (Faraone & Larsson, 2019). What has changed over the last decade is not the recognition of heritability itself, but our understanding of the genetic architecture behind it. For years, there was an expectation that a few genes of large effect - an "ADHD gene" - would be found. They weren't. Instead, it turns out that the risk is scattered across thousands of common variants, each influencing susceptibility in a marginal way, often at the very edge of detectability.

The largest genome-wide association study (GWAS) for ADHD to date (Demontis et al., 2023), comprising over 38,000 cases and 186,000 controls, managed to identify 27 loci where the genetic signal rose above the statistical noise. This is merely the tip of the iceberg: these 27 locations explain only a fraction of the total genetic influence. Collectively, common variants (estimated at around 7,000) account for roughly 22% of the phenotypic variance. The rest is distributed among variants too weak to be detected individually given current sample sizes.

This polygenic architecture is crucial for what I discuss in the following sections. When a trait depends on a small number of highly penetrant alleles, siblings can differ drastically in their risk depending on which alleles they happen to inherit. In a polygenic model, it works differently: risk scores are distributed roughly normally, and the siblings

of affected individuals, as a group, are shifted toward the higher end of this distribution. In practice, this means that in a family where one or both parents carry an elevated polygenic load for ADHD, all the children will tend to start with PRS values above the population average. Not just the one child who eventually ends up in a clinic (or doesn't, remaining a "naughty child" and later a "quirky adult").

And here the threshold problem arises: many of these children will never cross the clinical threshold for an ADHD diagnosis but will exhibit subthreshold traits. Difficulties sustaining attention, elevated motor activity, a preference for highly stimulating environments. These are traits that shape their subsequent development and interactions with caregivers, even if they never receive a diagnostic label.

Polygenic risk scores (PRS) allow us to predict not only categorical diagnoses but also the dimensional severity of symptoms, academic achievement, and a range of related behavioral phenotypes (Riglin et al., 2016). Most importantly, and central to the argument of this paper, PRS also predict environmental variables traditionally treated as causes of a child's behavior, rather than its consequences. Household chaos, parenting quality, family conflict (Agnew-Blais et al., 2022). This finding alone undermines the assumption that the home environment is something independent of the genetics of the child growing up within it.

Two additional aspects deserve emphasis. First, Demontis et al. (2023) demonstrated significant genetic correlations between ADHD and other neurodevelopmental disorders: approximately 84% of the variants associated with ADHD showed consistent effect directions with ASD risk variants. These cross-diagnostic correlations are not an incidental add-on here; they are foundational to the model, as they predict the assortative mating patterns discussed in Section 6.

Second, the polygenicity of ADHD implies something counterintuitive: the genetic basis of this disorder cannot be "bred out" by any pattern of partner selection. In a population where risk is scattered across thousands of loci, even the children of couples with no ADHD diagnosis will carry a non-trivial polygenic load. But in families with a high density of ADHD traits, this arithmetic compounds, which I will elaborate on later.

The clinical conclusion from all this is the following: the family environment in which a child predisposed to ADHD is born is, in part, a product of the very same genetic variants that the child carries. Parents who impose rigid daily schedules, who treat stillness as suspicious, who are constantly on the move themselves, are not doing this despite their genetics, but precisely because of it. This reciprocal relationship between genome and environment is the subject of the next two sections.

3. Compensatory Strategies Become Family Norms

Clinical literature concerning adult ADHD has long recognized that many individuals develop behavioral strategies to cope with their symptoms without ever receiving a formal diagnosis. Rigid scheduling, compulsive list-making, workaholicism, an intolerance for unstructured time. These strategies are typically described in individual terms, as personal adaptations to a neurobiological deficit. Much less is said about what happens when these strategies are sustained for decades, shared between partners, and passed down to children - not as coping mechanisms, but as imperatives from which there is no

deviation.

Before proceeding, however, we must address an argument that shapes public perception and, indirectly, the family environments being discussed. Namely: the claim that ADHD is a modern invention, that its prevalence is an artifact of a diagnostic fad rather than a biological reality. This view enjoys broad support and is structurally identical to the colloquial observation that "cancer is everywhere nowadays" or "everything causes cancer now, back in the day there was no cancer." In both cases, the reasoning confuses the availability of a diagnostic construct with the existence of the condition that the construct describes. People did not used to die of "old age" because old age killed them; they died of heart attacks, tumors, and strokes that no one knew how to identify. The same logic applies to ADHD.

Furthermore, the construct has a longer history than is commonly assumed. In 1902, George Still, in a series of lectures at the Royal College of Physicians in London, described 43 children with severe difficulties sustaining attention and controlling behavior. They were impulsive, resistant to discipline, and unable to learn from the consequences of their actions, despite having normal intelligence. Still gave this condition a name that sounds bizarre today: morbid defect of moral control. Crucially, however, even in 1902, Still attributed these difficulties to biological factors, not to poor upbringing. By the mid-20th century, the condition appeared as hyperkinetic reaction of childhood in DSM-II (1968), was reformulated as attention deficit disorder in DSM-III (1980), and was consolidated as ADHD in DSM-IV (1994). Adult ADHD remained largely invisible to clinical practice until the late 90s and was not widely accepted as a diagnostic entity until the 2000s.

In every previous generation, therefore, there lived people with these exact same difficulties. It's just that no one called it that.

Let us put ourselves in the shoes of a parent born in the 1960s who had ADHD, but neither they nor anyone around them knew such a thing existed. This person would experience chronic difficulties with attention, organization, and impulse regulation without any conceptual framework to understand them. The link between ADHD and compensatory overworking is not merely anecdotal: Andreassen et al. (2016), in a study of 16,426 Norwegian employees, found that 32.7% of individuals classified as workaholics met the clinical criteria for ADHD, compared to 12.7% among non-workaholics. ADHD symptoms were one of the strongest psychiatric predictors of work addiction. This supports the hypothesis that excessive work serves a self-regulatory function: it provides the continuous stimulation and external structural demands that an ADHD brain needs just to maintain an optimal level of arousal.

The strategies resulting from this dynamic take various forms depending on gender and social role. A man working 14 hours a day, incapable of resting, interprets this as ambition. A woman constantly bustling around the house with a cloth and broom, obsessively maintaining order, is perceived as neat and domestically capable; the dust settles constantly, so this strategy is never exhausted, making it practically ideal from a dopaminergic self-regulation perspective. In both cases, the behavior is experienced not as coping with a deficit, but as proof of discipline. Without a diagnostic label, the behavior simply becomes identity.

Canela et al. (2017), in a qualitative study of compensatory strategies in adults with ADHD, documented this process from the patients' perspective. Participants described developing rigid organizational routines long before their diagnosis and, crucially, described these routines as being instilled by parents who apparently intuitively recognized their children's difficulties and imposed structure as an attempt to remedy the observed behavioral struggles. Usually without any awareness of ADHD as a diagnostic entity. The parental intervention was adaptive, but carried a hidden message: that the child's natural behavioral tendencies are flawed and require constant external control.

And here we arrive at the core of this section. When this transformation of a compensatory strategy into an identity occurs in two individuals, and these two people form a household (which is made more likely by assortative mating, discussed in Section 6), their shared behavioral tendencies become the unwritten rules of the family system. Idleness is treated as something shameful, almost suspicious. Children in such a home do not learn that their parents are coping with attention deficits via hyperactivity. They learn that hyperactivity is the baseline expectation of a normally functioning human being - family is, after all, our first "whole world."

This mechanism has equivalents in systemic literature, particularly in the concept of parentification. In families with a high density of ADHD, a specific variant occurs: children are drafted into maintaining the compensatory architecture of the household, taking on the regulatory burden that the parents' neurology makes fragile. A child sitting and reading is not praised for their focus; they are asked what they are avoiding (just yesterday, a patient recounted: "My father barged into the room while I was reading on my bed and yelled, 'Why aren't you doing anything!'"). A child who needs downtime is told they are lazy.

This entire process is self-masking. Parents treat their behaviors as simply "right," unaware of their compensatory nature. The norm is invisible to those who enforce it because it was never articulated as a norm; it was experienced as a self-evident truth. In the clinic, this creates a characteristic picture: adults present with ADHD symptoms of exactly the severity one would expect based on their genetic liability (if WGS testing were more common, which I believe is warranted), yet they attribute their difficulties solely to being lazy, undisciplined, or simply failing to live up to the standards they were raised with.

To be fair, I must note that this specific hypothesis - that compensatory strategies crystallize into family norms with transgenerational consequences - has not, to my knowledge, been formally tested. The literature separately documents the existence of compensatory strategies in adults with ADHD (Canela et al., 2017) and the link between ADHD and workaholism (Andreassen et al., 2016). Combining these two threads into a hypothesis about the transmission of norms is a proposition born from clinical experience and awaits systematic validation.

Crucially, however, this connects to the next section: the environmental stressor in this scenario - the family norm demanding constant activity - is not independent of genetic risk. It was generated by the same polygenic liability the child inherited from the parents establishing those very norms. This is not a case of a random environmental factor happening to interact with a genetic predisposition. This is a case where the genotype constructs the environment, which will then interact with the genotype in the

next generation. This relationship has a name in science: gene-environment correlation.

4. Gene-Environment Correlation: The Child Shapes Its Own Environment

The traditional model of gene-environment interaction (GxE) assumes that genes and the environment are two independent sources of influence that together produce the observed clinical picture. The model is intuitive and statistically convenient, but in the context of highly heritable behavioral traits, it turns out to be woefully incomplete. The problem is not that gene-environment interactions do not occur. The problem is that, precisely in the case of traits like ADHD, the assumption that the environment is independent of genetics simply does not hold, because the environment is partially a product of those very same genes.

Gene-environment correlation (rGE) describes the systematic, non-random relationship between an individual's genotype and the environments they are exposed to. Plomin, DeFries, and Loehlin (1977) distinguished three forms, and this taxonomy, though nearly half a century old, still perfectly organizes our thinking about this phenomenon. Passive rGE stems from the fact that children share both their genes and their rearing environment with their biological parents: a child born into a family with high polygenic loading for ADHD simultaneously carries more risk alleles and grows up in a home organized around undiagnosed attentional dysfunction. Evocative rGE occurs when a child's genetically influenced traits elicit specific reactions from their surroundings: a restless, impulsive, inattentive child provokes frustration, harsh parenting, and eventually, often a diagnostic referral (though that is arguably a good outcome). Active rGE reflects the child's own selection of environments: a thrill-seeking teenager gravitates toward peer groups offering intense stimulation; an inattentive student avoids academic environments requiring sustained focus, and so on.

All three forms operate simultaneously in families with high ADHD loading. This is not a theoretical curiosity. Their combined effect blurs the line between what, in a phenotypic analysis, looks like a genetic effect and what looks like an environmental effect. It has very concrete consequences for how we interpret studies on "environmental" risk factors for ADHD.

Two recent empirical studies illustrate this exceptionally well.

Agnew-Blais et al. (2022) investigated the relationship between maternal and child ADHD PRS, household chaos, and child ADHD symptoms in the British E-Risk twin cohort, comprising over 2,200 twins followed since age 5. The result was that children with elevated ADHD PRS lived in significantly more chaotic home environments. Not because chaos was randomly distributed in the population, but because both the child's genetically influenced behavior and the mother's polygenic liability contributed to the disorganization of the home. Once the polygenic risk of both mother and child was accounted for, household chaos turned out to be a much weaker predictor of symptoms than earlier analyses suggested. In other words: what looked like an independent environmental factor largely reflected the genetic liability of the family.

Nikolas et al. (2023) extended this logic to parenting behaviors. The ADHD PRS of young people predicted not only the course of their own symptoms but also the quality of parenting they received. Higher polygenic risk was associated with more difficult parenting relationships, largely because the child's challenging behaviors provoked harsher parental reactions. The pathway led from genotype, through child behavior, to parental response, to the reinforcement of the initial phenotype. The loop closes.

An important methodological caveat applies to both studies, and it must be emphasized. The structural equation models and mediation analyses on which these papers rely are fitted to observational data. While the results are consistent with an rGE interpretation, they do not constitute formal proof of causality: unmeasured confounding variables, reverse causality, and model specification choices can influence the estimated pathways. The gene-environment correlation framework is best understood as a well-supported theoretical model with convergent empirical evidence, rather than a mechanism proven in a strict experimental sense.

What emerges is a picture in which a child with high polygenic ADHD loading is born into an environment already shaped by the parents' genetic liability (passive rGE), provokes the intensification of that environment through their behavior (evocative rGE), and gradually selects contexts that reinforce the predisposition (active rGE). At no point in this sequence is the environment independent of the genome.

However, stating that environments are partially genetically determined does not mean they are unchangeable, nor does it mean that interventions are pointless. Quite the opposite. It means that effective help must take this loop into account. Psychotherapy that helps a patient recognize compensatory family norms as something born in specific circumstances, rather than as a universal truth about how one must live, operates on a different level than merely treating symptoms. Lifestyle changes that increase access to stimulation in a controlled manner (sports, changing work environments, conscious planning of rest) address neurobiological needs instead of masking them with compulsive activity. But none of these interventions will fully work if they fail to acknowledge that the environment we are trying to influence is partially a product of the very genes we are trying to support. This is, in fact, how I am inclined to understand the mechanism of psychotherapy: as the conscious support of development taking into account predispositions arising from innate genetic potential.

5. Epigenetic Mechanisms: When Family Norms Can Activate Genetic Potential

The previous sections demonstrated that families with high ADHD loading generate environments that are both the product of parental genetic liability and, frequently, a source of chronic stress for the offspring. The question that arises is: Can this environmental pressure, at least in principle, leave biological marks?

The DNA sequence is set in stone from conception to death, but it can be "read" in different ways depending on the conditions in which a person grows up. DNA methylation - the addition of methyl groups to cytosines at specific sequence sites (so-called CpG dinucleotides) - is the best-understood mechanism by which the environment can influence which genes are active and which are silenced, without any

change to the sequence itself. Methylation patterns are established during prenatal development and early childhood, respond to environmental cues (stress, nutrition, relationships with caregivers), and can persist throughout life. In practice, this means that two individuals with identical DNA can function differently, as if they had different genetic material, because methylation dictates which genes are actively transcribed into traits and which remain silenced.

There are three preliminary lines of evidence supporting the operation of this mechanism in the context of ADHD. I emphasize: preliminary.

First, Mooney et al. (2020) conducted a large epigenome-wide association study in children with and without ADHD. They identified differentially methylated regions associated with an ADHD diagnosis and showed that ADHD polygenic risk scores themselves correlated with specific methylation patterns. This suggests an additional feedback loop superimposed on the gene-environment correlation described in the previous section: genotype shapes environment, environment modifies the way the genotype is read, and the modified readout alters the expression of traits. This sounds speculative, but the data points in this direction, at least within a single generation.

Second, Fujisawa et al. (2022) studied monozygotic twins discordant for ADHD - pairs with identical genomes but differing expressed traits. They found differential methylation in the *SorCS2* gene, which is involved in neurotrophin signaling (crucial for the development and survival of neurons), and showed that these differences were associated with variations in gray matter volume. This is an important study because if identical twins have identical DNA yet one has ADHD and the other does not, the differences must arise elsewhere: in the environment, over the course of development, or precisely in how those same genes are read.

Third, Cecil et al. (2022), in a review of ADHD epigenetics, synthesized the available evidence. Their conclusions were cautiously supportive: numerous studies have identified ADHD-associated methylation differences in genes relevant to neurodevelopment and stress response, but effect sizes are generally small, replication is inconsistent, and the direction of causality (whether methylation changes precede symptoms or are a consequence of them) remains unresolved. The state of knowledge is thus: the mechanism exists, preliminary data are consistent with it, but we are far from certainty. Is this enough to include it in the model? I believe so, with appropriate caveats.

And here I must be perfectly clear, as intellectual honesty demands it. All the epigenetic literature cited here documents methylation differences within a single generation: between individuals with and without ADHD, or between discordant twins. It does not demonstrate transgenerational epigenetic inheritance in the strict sense - i.e., the transmission of environmentally induced methylation changes from parent to child via germ cells. Such inheritance has been documented in animal models (yes, in mice, of course) and is supported by suggestive data from human cohorts subjected to extreme famine (studies on descendants of the Dutch Hunger Winter of 1944-1945). However, for ADHD or any specific psychiatric disorder, it has not yet been proven.

The argument of this paper therefore rests on a cautious assertion: the molecular mechanism capable of such changes exists; methylation changes have been linked to ADHD in intra-generational studies; and the environments generated by families with

high ADHD loading are the type of early-life stressors that broader literature identifies as capable of inducing lasting epigenomic modifications. The transgenerational extension remains a hypothesis, which I consider plausible but unproven. I prefer to state this plainly rather than hide it in fine print caveats.

It is also worth noting something that extends beyond ADHD. The epigenetic mechanisms described here are not specific to this single disorder. If chronic early-life stress modifies methylation in genes involved in stress response and neurotransmitter regulation, the consequences could include elevated vulnerability to a much broader spectrum of psychiatric conditions. The loop described in this article may therefore be one variant of a more general mechanism wherein environments generated by parents with psychiatric disorders epigenetically expand the vulnerability space in their offspring. But that is a topic for a separate paper.

6. Assortative Mating: The Cumulation of Neurodivergence

The mechanisms described so far operate within families. But families do not form at random. The selection of a reproductive partner is a phenotypically and genetically non-random process, and in the context of psychological traits, this non-randomness has consequences that span across generations.

Nordsletten et al. (2016), in a population-based registry study encompassing over 700,000 psychiatric patients in Sweden, showed that non-random mating was the rule, not the exception, across 11 major psychiatric disorders. Individuals with an ADHD diagnosis significantly more often mated with others with ADHD. But even more striking were the cross-diagnostic patterns: individuals with ADHD mated with individuals with ASD and, at odds ratios exceeding 9 in some pairings, with individuals diagnosed with schizophrenia.

These associations may be surprising. Looking at a textbook description, ADHD, ASD, and schizophrenia look entirely different: impulsive sociability, social withdrawal, impaired reality testing. And yet, people with these diagnoses form couples far more frequently than chance would dictate. Why, when the clinical labels suggest such different worlds?

This phenomenon can be explained in three mutually complementary ways.

The first is a shared genetic architecture. Grove et al. (2022) demonstrated that ADHD and ASD share a substantial portion of their common-variant genetic base, with about 84% of ADHD risk variants showing concordant effect directions for ASD. An individual with a high polygenic load for ADHD will therefore, on average, also carry a moderately elevated load for ASD and exhibit subtle traits of both conditions. Traits that may facilitate mutual recognition and attraction long before anyone considers a diagnosis, because the severity of symptoms resulting from polygenic loading will not necessarily be a problem; it will be more developmentally attuned to the age at which we typically meet partners, experienced as attractive, making the partner stand out from the crowd.

The second is phenotypic selection prior to diagnosis. Assortative mating occurs on the basis of observable traits, not diagnostic labels. A person with undiagnosed ADHD, drawn to novelty and intellectual unconventionality, may find a natural partner in

someone whose undiagnosed ASD manifests as deep intellectual focus and direct communication. The diagnosis, if it comes at all, arrives later. Couples therapists know this pattern well and speak of a "complementary couple": what initially attracted them (he is spontaneous, she is organized; he is outgoing, she is focused) eventually begins to irritate. I know this as a common phenomenon from my own couples therapy practice.

The third is shared social ecology. In the classroom, on the playground, at university, individuals with neurodevelopmental traits often end up on the fringes of the mainstream peer group. Research on peer dynamics indicates that children rejected by the mainstream form friendships with other rejected peers (Dijkstra et al., 2010), and children with ADHD are among the most frequently socially rejected groups in a classroom (Hoza et al., 2005). Autistic individuals exhibit a tendency to befriend other atypical individuals because they can be themselves around them (Crompton et al., 2020). Those peripheral groups of nerds, artists, and the positively eccentric that everyone remembers from school are not a random clustering; it is homophily in action. Later, these same people meet in professional niches that reward atypical thinking (IT, art, science, entrepreneurship), and relationships grow from these encounters.

The genetic consequence of assortative mating is additive. When both parents carry an elevated polygenic load, the expected PRS of the offspring is shifted upward relative to the population mean. When mating occurs between individuals with different disorders (ADHD with ASD, ADHD with SCZ), the offspring inherits an elevated load for multiple disorders simultaneously. This is the genetic basis for the increasingly recognized "AuDHD" phenotype: individuals meeting criteria for both ADHD and ASD. Probably not because of a single shared etiology, but because parental selection concentrated risk variants for both disorders into a single genome.

Pleiotropy adds another layer. Because many of the same genetic variants simultaneously affect ADHD, ASD, and schizophrenia, mating based on one disorder inadvertently increases the offspring's risk for the others. The effect multiplies, it doesn't just add up.

And here emerges a paradox that motivated me to conduct my own analyses: if individuals with ADHD and schizophrenia mate at such high odds ratios, why are their polygenic risk scores not correlated with each other? The data I present in the next section points to the resolution.

6b. Causal Pathways Between Schizophrenia, ADHD, and Autism Spectrum Disorder: Evidence from Mendelian Randomization

To verify whether the observed cross-diagnostic associations reflect genuine causal relationships rather than merely the co-occurrence of genetic variants, I conducted two-sample Mendelian randomization (MR) analyses. This method utilizes genetic variants as instrumental variables: because alleles are randomly assigned at conception, if variants that reliably increase susceptibility to one disorder simultaneously predict an elevated risk of another, this serves as an argument for a causal relationship. The full methodological description can be found in the Materials

and Methods section; here, I present the key findings and their implications for the proposed model.

Detailed statistical results, confidence intervals, and p-values for all analyses are presented in Figures 1-6.

Starting point: correlations of polygenic risk scores. In a reference sample of 525 unrelated individuals of European ancestry from the 1000 Genomes Project, polygenic risk scores for the three disorders exhibited a characteristic pattern (Fig. 1). PRS for ADHD and ASD were moderately correlated, PRS for SCZ and ASD weakly but significantly, whereas PRS for schizophrenia and ADHD showed practically no correlation. This last result is puzzling in light of the data by Nordsletten et al. (2016) regarding the high odds ratio of ADHD-schizophrenia mating.

Rys. 1. Korelacje poligenicznych wyników ryzyka dla schizofrenii (SCZ), ADHD i zaburzenia ze spektrum autyzmu (ASD) (N = 525, 1000 Genomes Project). Macierz korelacji i rozkłady PRS. Model ADHD: PGS002746 (Demontis 2019).

I confirmed this result by calculating the ADHD PRS using a newer and better-powered GWAS (Demontis et al., 2023; 52,329 variants after LD pruning): the SCZ-ADHD correlation remained non-significant ($r = 0.050$; $p = 0.256$), while the ASD-ADHD correlation was almost identical to the model based on the older GWAS ($r = 0.179$ vs $r = 0.189$). The lack of correlation between individual PRS for schizophrenia and ADHD is therefore not an artifact of insufficient model power. This highlights a crucial

distinction: although population studies demonstrate a global genetic correlation (r_g) between these disorders, this does not translate into a strong correlation of predictive polygenic profiles at the individual level. Genetic similarity alone is therefore incapable of explaining such high mating rates.

ADHD Polygenic Risk Score Comparison: Demontis 2019 (PGS002746) vs Demontis 2023 (52,329 SNPs)
N = 525 unrelated individuals of European ancestry (1000 Genomes Project)

Rys. 1b. Porównanie modeli PRS ADHD: Demontis 2019 (PGS002746) vs Demontis 2023 (52 329 SNP po pruning LD). Korelacja SCZ-ADHD pozostaje nieistotna niezależnie od modelu.

Asymmetrical causality resolves the paradox. The MR analyses revealed that the causal relationships between these disorders are not symmetrical (Fig. 2). Genetic liability to schizophrenia causally increased the risk of both ASD and ADHD. In the opposite direction, liability to ADHD (using the newest GWAS; Demontis et al., 2023) showed a strong causal effect on ASD risk and a significant effect on schizophrenia risk. For autism spectrum disorders, an analogous analysis could not be performed because the available genetic data did not provide a sufficient number of statistical instruments (after the selection procedure, only 1 SNP remained, precluding reliable MR analysis).

Rys. 2. Główne wyniki randomizacji mendelowskiej: efekty przyczynowe między SCZ, ADHD i ASD (metoda IVW). Ekspozycja ADHD: Demontis 2023.

The results from two versions of the ADHD GWAS (Demontis et al., 2019 vs. 2023; Fig. 5) are presented intentionally to demonstrate the impact of instrument strength on causal inference. The 2023 dataset includes the earlier sample and is significantly larger (38,691 cases, 186,843 controls), providing more genetic instruments after the selection procedure. With the weaker instrument set from 2019, the ADHD-to-schizophrenia pathway did not reach statistical significance; with the stronger 2023 set, it became significant. This indicates that the earlier null result was due to insufficient statistical power, not the absence of a true relationship.

Checking the reliability of results. I conducted additional sensitivity analyses to verify if the results remain stable regardless of the statistical method applied (Fig. 3-4). Four different MR methods yielded consistent effect directions for all significant pathways. For one of the pathways (schizophrenia to ASD), however, I cannot rule out that the observed effect partially stems from the fact that the same genes influence both disorders simultaneously (pleiotropy), rather than from a direct causal relationship.

Rys. 3. Analiza sprawdzająca: cztery metody MR dla wszystkich par ekspozycja-wynik. Instrumenty ADHD: Demontis 2023.

Sensitivity Analysis: ADHD (Demontis 2023) → ASD and SCZ

IWW and Weighted Median converge for both outcomes; larger effect on ASD (OR=1.58) than SCZ (OR=1.27) | OR (95% CI, log scale)

Exposure: ADHD Demontis 2023 Jan2022 Release (N_{ADHD}=38,691; N_{ADHD}=186,843) | 26 instruments after LD clumping (p<5×10⁻⁸, r²<0.001)
 Outcomes: ASD (ieu-a-1185; Grove 2019) | SCZ (ieu-b-5099; Trubetsky 2022 PGC3)
 MR-Egger intercepts non-significant for both directions (p=0.68 and p=0.41); Steiger filtering confirmed causal direction

Rys. 4. Analiza sprawdzająca: ADHD (Demontis 2023) jako ekspozycja na ASD i SCZ. Cztery metody MR.

Bidirectional Mendelian Randomization: SCZ / ADHD / ASD (Demontis 2019)

IWW estimates | ADHD-SCZ did not reach significance (n=10 instruments; Demontis 2019) — contrast with Demontis 2023 in Figure 2

ADHD: Demontis et al. 2019 (ieu-a-1183, N_{ADHD}=20,183) | SCZ: Trubetsky et al. 2022 PGC3 (ieu-b-5099, N_{SCZ}=76,755)
 ASD (Grove 2019, ieu-a-1185): insufficient instruments for ASD-as-exposure analysis (1 SNP after palindrome removal)
 Clumping: p<5×10⁻⁷, r²<0.001, 10,000kb, EUR | Steiger filtering confirmed causal direction for all analysed pairs

Rys. 5. Dwukierunkowa MR z instrumentami ADHD Demontis 2019 dla porównania z Rys. 2. Ścieżka ADHD-SCZ nie osiąga istotności (OR = 1,15; p = 0,063).

Limitations. The inability to test ASD as an exposure means that the question of the causal impact of autism liability on ADHD and schizophrenia risk remains open. The reference sample for the PRS correlations (N = 525) is small for polygenic analyses, and these results should be treated as orientational. The PRS model for schizophrenia was based on an older GWAS (PGC2, 2018), whereas newer data (PGC3, Trubetsky 2022) were used in the MR analyses. High heterogeneity in results with the 2023 ADHD and schizophrenia instruments is expected given such highly polygenic exposures, but it means the main estimates represent averages of potentially heterogeneous effects.

What this means for the intergenerational model. The discovery of asymmetrical causal effects between these disorders allows us to propose an explanation for the paradox I began this section with. If genetic liability to ADHD increases the risk of traits

similar to schizophrenia (and vice versa), then at the level of daily functioning, these individuals may have more in common than their polygenic scores would suggest. Mating would therefore occur based on observable similarities shaped by the causal impact of one disorder on the other, not on the basis of shared genetic variants. The offspring of such couples would inherit variants that do not simply overlap, but mutually interact with one another - a distinction that simple PRS correlations are unable to capture.

This hypothesis requires direct empirical verification, but it is consistent with both epidemiological mating data (Nordsletten et al., 2016) and the MR results presented here.

7. Clinical Implications

The model developed in this paper has implications that extend far beyond the diagnostic clinic. If ADHD is not merely an individual's disorder but an element of an intergenerational system where genes, family norms, and partner selection co-create a loop, treating just the symptoms in the individual will not suffice, because the system generating them continues to operate.

Three levels of clinical assessment. Conventional ADHD diagnostics focus on the presenting individual: how many symptoms, how severe the impairment, when did it begin. The model presented here suggests that assessment should routinely encompass three interconnected levels.

The first is the individual level, i.e., standard diagnostic assessment supplemented by dimensional measures of attentional and executive functions. The second, often overlooked, is the family of origin level. And an important note here: the goal is not merely to ask whether there was ADHD in the family (because in the generation of parents and grandparents, almost no one was diagnosed), but to explore the norms that governed the household. What were the unwritten rules regarding rest, idleness, productivity? Did sitting still provoke criticism or anxiety among family members? Was anyone in the family capable of resting without feeling guilty? A patient who answers "no" to the question about family history of ADHD may simultaneously describe a home whose operating rules were transparently compensatory. The third is the partner level: the neurocognitive profile of the partner, which is particularly important when the patient reports relationship conflicts or concerns about their children's development. Data on assortative mating (Nordsletten et al., 2016) indicate that the partner of a person with ADHD has a significantly elevated probability of having their own ADHD, ASD, or other neurodevelopmental traits.

Destigmatization through understanding the mechanism. One of the most destructive aspects of ADHD in the patient's experience is the persistent attribution of symptoms to personal failure: laziness, lack of discipline, insufficient willpower. The intergenerational model allows this narrative to be reframed. A patient raised in a home where constant activity was an unquestionable requirement is not lazy because he failed to meet this standard. He is reacting to a demand that was itself a symptom of the disorder he inherited (or at least the susceptibility to it). The family norm he fails to measure up to was never a rational criterion for a good life; it was a compensatory

artifact generated by the neurobiology of previous generations.

Articulating this in psychoeducation can break the cycle of self-condemnation that plagues many adults with ADHD. However, this must be done carefully, and I consider this caveat crucial. The goal is not to replace moral blaming with genetic determinism, but to provide a more accurate causal model in which genetic predisposition, family environment, and individual agency are all recognized as real and mutually interacting. The patient is not responsible for their polygenic load, nor for the norms they internalized before they were capable of evaluating them critically. They are, however, capable of recognizing these norms as acquired, not eternal, and of gradually building their own ways of functioning once they understand where the expectations they grew up with came from.

Paradoxically, the biopsychosocial model, which has been the official foundation of psychiatry and clinical psychology for decades, provides ready-made frameworks for this. Biology (polygenic load), psychology (internalized norms, compensatory strategies), and social context (family system, partner selection) are not separate layers, but mutually shape one another. In practice, however, many therapists working individually focus on the individual psychological layer, treating biology as a distant backdrop and the family system as mere context rather than an active mechanism. What I propose suggests that effective intervention requires working on all three levels simultaneously, or at the very least being aware that they interact (though in my view, mere awareness is highly insufficient for effective work).

The ADHD and ASD couple in systemic therapy. Data on assortative mating suggest that a considerable proportion of couples presenting for therapy will consist of one partner with ADHD traits and the other with ASD traits, or, increasingly, both carrying traits of both disorders. The typical complaints in such couples ("he never listens" versus "she never says directly what she wants"; "he's always on the go" versus "she needs everything planned"; "she constantly wants to do something, plans trips and outings" versus "he would just sit in his garage and tinker") correspond to predictable neurocognitive differences, partly inherited and partly complementary.

A systemic therapist working with such a pair must recognize that the source of the conflict is not primarily communication or good/bad intentions (though after years of exhausting attempts to communicate without accounting for differing neurocognitive profiles, intentions can indeed sour), but different default modes of information processing, where each partner experiences their own as self-evident and the other's as incomprehensible. Psychoeducation regarding the neurobiological and genetic foundations of these differences - framed not as an excuse, but as an explanation - can reduce mutual blaming and create space for accommodation instead of attempts to "fix" the partner. My experience in couples therapy indicates that the very moment this mechanism is named in a session can be a breakthrough: partners suddenly see that it is not a matter of malice, but of differently wired nervous systems.

Offspring in high-liability families. When both parents carry elevated polygenic risk, children are exposed to measurably higher risk - not just for one specific disorder, but across a broad vulnerability space encompassing ADHD, ASD, and related phenotypes. Clinicians working with such families should be alert to the possibility that a child's symptoms reflect a convergence of multiple parental genetic contributions, rather than a single isolated diagnostic entity. The increasingly common clinical picture

of AuDHD (children meeting criteria for both ADHD and ASD) is a predictable outcome of the mating patterns discussed in this paper and the shared genetic architecture of both conditions.

What next: directions for future research. The presented model generates several testable predictions. Longitudinal studies simultaneously tracking PRS, family norms, methylation patterns, and offspring phenotypes in the same cohorts would allow a direct test of the proposed loop. Partner concordance studies using PRS instead of diagnostic categories could more precisely estimate the genetic consequences of assortative mating. Finally, interventional studies targeting compensatory family norms (rather than individual symptoms) could evaluate whether breaking the transmission pathway of norms translates into measurable changes in the offspring. If so, it would constitute the strongest possible proof that the loop described here actually operates.

There is one more scenario that deserves research attention, which I know from clinical practice. Let us imagine a 2+2 family: both parents with high polygenic loading, two children. One child drew enough in the genetic lottery to clearly exhibit ADHD traits themselves, gives the parents a run for their money, fuels the home chaos, and paradoxically confirms the family norm because they fit into it like a key in a lock. But the second child drew relatively few risk alleles. They are calm, can sit still with a book, and do not need constant stimulation. In the general population, they would function perfectly normally. Except they do not live in the general population; they live in this specific home, where norms have been calibrated to a neurobiology they did not inherit. Their calmness will be interpreted as withdrawal, perhaps laziness, or a sign that "something is wrong." The parents may worry or criticize, unaware that the child is not the problem - their household criteria for normality are. How does such a situation affect the development of a child who is healthy in a sick system? This is a question for which we do not yet have data, but which I consider clinically urgent.

8. Conclusions

This paper has argued that the intergenerational transmission of ADHD-related phenotypes cannot be adequately understood through a purely genetic or purely environmental lens. Evidence gathered from behavioral genetics, molecular psychiatry, clinical psychology, and epidemiology points to a recursive system in which five mechanisms interact, forming a closed loop. Polygenic risk dispersed among thousands of variants means that entire sibships in affected families start with an elevated load. The compensatory behavioral strategies of parents who were never diagnosed crystallize into family norms that function as chronic stressors. Gene-environment correlation means that the child's behavior shapes the very environment that acts upon them. Preliminary epigenetic data suggest that chronic early-life stress may modify how genes are read, although the transgenerational nature of this mechanism in humans remains unproven. Finally, non-random assortative mating concentrates neurodevelopmental risk across diagnostic boundaries, creating offspring whose genetic liability encompasses ADHD, ASD, and related disorders simultaneously.

The original Mendelian randomization analyses presented in this paper add a causal dimension to this picture. The discovery that liability to ADHD causally increases the risk of autism, and liability to schizophrenia causally increases the risk of both ADHD

and ASD, shows that the cross-diagnostic associations underlying assortative mating are not merely correlational artifacts of a shared genetic architecture. They reflect directional biological pathways that cannot be captured by simple correlations of polygenic risk scores. The asymmetry of these causal relationships resolves the apparent paradox between high odds ratios of assortative mating and the weak correlation of their PRS scores at the individual level.

I want to reiterate two caveats at the end, as I consider them important. First, the epigenetic component remains the most speculative element of the model. The molecular mechanism capable of environmentally induced methylation changes is well understood, and preliminary evidence in the context of ADHD is consistent with it, but the definitive demonstration of epigenetic transmission between generations in humans has not yet been achieved. I treat this mechanism as plausible and theoretically motivated, not as empirically proven. Second, the clinical observations motivating this paper - compensatory family norms, the endless bustling, the passing down of demands to children whose source no one in the family recognizes - stem from my therapeutic practice. This is a hypothesis growing out of the consultation room, not an established fact, and it awaits systematic research that could confirm or refute it.

What is not speculative is the central observation of this paper: in families with high polygenic loading for ADHD, the genome builds the environment, the environment shapes the expression of the genome, and the resulting phenotype selects a partner whose genome restarts the cycle. The conventional dichotomy between nature and nurture is, in this context, not so much unhelpful as it is biologically incoherent. Future research should measure the strength of each mechanism described here, both separately and in mutual interaction. The ultimate goal is an intervention that does not end with treating symptoms in a single patient, but reaches into the intergenerational system that produces those symptoms.

Materials and Methods

Study Design. This paper combines a theoretical review of mechanisms of intergenerational ADHD transmission with original empirical analyses: (1) correlations of polygenic risk scores (PRS) and (2) two-sample Mendelian randomization (MR). All analyses utilized publicly available summary statistics and reference genotype data; no individual clinical data were collected.

PRS Correlation Analyses.

Reference Sample. Polygenic risk scores were calculated for 525 unrelated individuals of European ancestry from the 1000 Genomes Project Phase 3 (Auton et al., 2015). Kinship filtering (KING kinship < 0.0884) and ancestry confirmation via principal component analysis were performed in PLINK 2.0.

PRS Models. Three PRS were calculated from pre-computed models obtained from the PGS Catalog: PGS002785 (schizophrenia, based on Pardini et al., 2018), PGS002746 (ADHD, based on Demontis et al., 2019), and PGS002790 (ASD, based on Grove et al., 2019). An additional ADHD PRS was constructed from the summary statistics of Demontis et al. (2023; iPSYCH1 + iPSYCH2 + deCODE + PGC; 38,691 cases, 186,843 controls; January 2022 release) obtained from the iPSYCH consortium following a data

access agreement. This dataset is not publicly available via OpenGWAS or PGS Catalog. The file contained 6,774,224 SNPs mapped to GRCh37 (hg19) with effect sizes reported as odds ratios, which were log-transformed prior to scoring. LD pruning was performed in PLINK 2.0 ($r^2 < 0.1$, window 250 kb), yielding 52,329 variants for the 2023 model. All PRS were standardized to z-scores prior to analysis.

Statistical Analysis. Pearson and Spearman correlations were calculated between all PRS pairs. Confidence intervals were obtained via Fisher's z transformation. All analyses were performed in R 4.3.1.

Two-Sample Mendelian Randomization.

Data Sources. GWAS summary statistics used as exposures and outcomes: Schizophrenia: Trubetskoy et al. (2022), PGC3 (ieu-b-5099; $N_{\text{case}} = 76,755$). ADHD (2019): Demontis et al. (2019), via OpenGWAS (ieu-a-1183; $N_{\text{case}} = 20,183$). ADHD (2023): Demontis et al. (2023), local summary statistics from iPSYCH ($N_{\text{case}} = 38,691$; $N_{\text{control}} = 186,843$). ASD: Grove et al. (2019), iPSYCH-PGC (ieu-a-1185; $N_{\text{case}} = 18,382$).

Instrument Selection. Genome-wide significant SNPs ($p < 5 \times 10^{-8}$) were selected as instruments. LD clumping was performed using a European reference panel ($r^2 < 0.001$, window 10,000 kb). Palindromic SNPs with intermediate allele frequencies were removed. ASD could not be used as an exposure because, after clumping and palindromic SNP removal, only 1 SNP remained (Grove et al., 2019).

MR Methods. The primary analysis utilized the Inverse Variance Weighted (IVW) method. Sensitivity analyses included weighted median, weighted mode, and MR-Egger regression. Steiger directionality filtering was applied to confirm the correct causal orientation. Cochran's Q statistic was used to assess heterogeneity. The MR-Egger intercept was evaluated for potential directional pleiotropy. All MR analyses were performed using the TwoSampleMR package (version 0.5.7) in R 4.3.1.

Instrument Strength. The number of instruments per analysis ranged from 10 (ADHD 2019 as exposure on SCZ) to 179 (SCZ as exposure on ASD). F-statistics for individual instruments were calculated as $F = \beta^2 / \text{se}^2$; all instruments exceeded the conventional threshold of $F > 10$, indicating adequate instrument strength.

Use of Artificial Intelligence. Large language models (LLMs) were utilized to assist with programming (including Python and R scripting for data processing and formatting) and to aid in the drafting and language editing of the manuscript. As the sole author, I take full and ultimate responsibility for the entire content, methodology, analyses, and conclusions presented in this work.

Ethics and Data Availability. All analyses utilized publicly available summary statistics and reference panel data. No individual clinical data were collected. The 1000 Genomes Project data are publicly available. GWAS summary statistics for SCZ and ASD were obtained via OpenGWAS (MRC IEU). ADHD 2023 summary statistics were obtained under a data access agreement with the iPSYCH consortium. Analytical code is available from the author upon request.

Author Contributions. Lukasz Lewandowski designed the study, conducted all analyses, and wrote the manuscript.

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Glossary of Key Terms

Assortative Mating. The tendency to choose partners who are similar concerning a given trait. Here: the elevated probability that individuals with ADHD form relationships with partners with ADHD, ASD, or SCZ.

CpG Dinucleotide. A site in DNA where a cytosine is followed by a guanine. The primary target for DNA methylation.

DNA Methylation. The addition of a methyl group to a cytosine. It can silence genes without altering the underlying sequence. Responds to environmental stress.

Epigenetics. The study of changes in gene activity without changes to the DNA sequence. Allows the environment to influence gene expression.

Gene-Environment Correlation (rGE). A non-random relationship between genotype and environment. Three types: passive (shared genes and home), evocative (child's behavior provokes reactions), active (seeking out fitting environments).

GWAS (Genome-Wide Association Study). An examination of the entire genome of thousands of people to identify variants associated with a trait. The foundation for calculating PRS.

Heritability. The proportion of phenotypic variance in a population attributable to genetics. $0.80 = 80\%$ of the variance in the population is genetic; it does not mean 80% of a specific individual's trait is genetic.

Mendelian Randomization (MR). A method utilizing genetic variants as natural experiments for causal inference. Alleles randomly assigned at conception approximate the logic of a randomized trial.

Odds Ratio (OR). A measure of association strength. $OR = 1.5$ indicates a 50% increase in the odds of an outcome per unit increase in exposure.

Pleiotropy. The phenomenon wherein a single genetic variant influences more than one trait.

PRS (Polygenic Risk Score). A single number summarizing genetic liability, calculated from thousands of GWAS variants. A higher PRS indicates higher predisposition, but not a clinical diagnosis.

SNP (Single Nucleotide Polymorphism). A variation at a single position in a DNA sequence. A common type of genetic variation. Individually they have small effects, but collectively they are significant.

Genetic Correlation (rg). A measure of the global genetic overlap between two traits at the population level, calculated via LD Score Regression. It must be distinguished from correlations of individual PRS scores, which describe the relationship at the individual level.

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